

HOW RESTAURANT ENTERPRISES MANAGE LOYALTY OF GUESTS IN EFFECTIVE WAYS

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Мирсоатова Лайло Мирвохид кизи

Студентка направления Туризм
Технический институт Ёджу в городе Ташкент

Abstract: *The research paper demonstrates the how to keep guests loyal in the restaurant, as a set of measures aimed at creating a guest experience in restaurant by providing individual and exclusive offers.*

Keywords: *Loyalty programs of restaurant Businesses, Customer service, guests.*

1.Introduction

Guest loyalty management is not only a full-fledged section of PR, advertising and marketing, but also regular management of a hospitality company. Loyalty is a very airy, almost intangible and unstable "psychological " connection. Since the beginning of the 20th century, owners of various businesses have been actively using all kinds of flyers that give the right to discounts on products. These promotions often had a wide scale and were very popular with buyers. But, like any system, these promotions had a drawback – it was not possible to collect and summarize customer data, conduct an analysis of promotions in order to determine the target group of consumers. So, a vegetarian could get a discount coupon from the dairy department when buying a pot. All this was due to the fact that the relationship with the consumer was one-sided.

2.Problem Statement

With the advent of modern cash register software and the development of catalogue trading, loyalty programs have reached a completely different level – and building a dialogue with the consumer is in the foreground. The greatest development occurred in the 60s of the last century, when plastic cards appeared. First of all, entrepreneurs began to evaluate the probability of organizing and maintaining a customer database. Moreover, restaurant business owners were no longer focused on revenue growth indicators .The quality service that is provided at most restaurants are at low level .

2.1 Changes in The format of Restaurant business. Today, the market for loyalty programs, most of which are based on the use of plastic cards, is very wide. For example, the average resident has 13 discount cards (a resident of large cities is about 30-50), and it is not used commonly , and at least a third of them do not even remember! As a result, in order to develop an effective and efficient loyalty program, it is necessary to take into account the factor of usefulness and desirability of a particular privilege. The benefits

provided should have value for a strictly defined category of users. Currently, there are two main types of loyalty card programs that are used in the restaurant business, at enterprises of various formats(1).

4. Discussions.

Create a personal account on the restaurant's website. One of the most modern ways to encourage guests is to create a personal account on the restaurant's own website(2-P.38). This introduction allows you to expand the range of opportunities for a potential consumer:

- choosing a table in online mode with further booking of the one you like table size;
- possibility of preliminary acquaintance of the consumer with new dishes, presented in the menu;
- getting acquainted with promotions and upcoming events;
- view interior solutions of restaurant halls.

Creating office supplies. The stylish daily planner will undoubtedly draw the guest's attention to a curious and entertaining event opposite the festive date and will remind you about our restaurant for the whole coming year.

Dissemination of information about restaurant events. A classic modern way to inform the guest about various events via email. And in no case should you encroach on your personal space guest: mailing lists should not be intrusive, and the guest should be able to unsubscribe from them at any time.

Maintaining a restaurant group (club) in social networks. One of the dynamically developing types of information is the creation of a group in social networks "Vkontakte", "Facebook", which allows you to draw the attention of the most active and energetic users to our restaurant.

Catering services. A dynamically developing area that has already gained wide popularity is the provision of field service services. The direction is quite profitable, and the provision of services can be either full or partial, for example, the provision of services for creating an event scenario or providing a hall for holding a themed party and drawing up a menu.

Own programs. Accumulative cards are a promising way to attract potential consumers due to the gradual increase in the number of bonuses and savings on the card. If discount cards are provided with the necessary software that allows you to create a detailed database that tracks a lot of criteria, then it can serve you well. The perspective of creating complex programs is as follows. You can increase and accumulate points using a single card. Facilitating the organization of various events. But, most importantly, it is a huge tool for attracting customers. The presence of bonus points on the card again attracts customers to our restaurant. Loyalty programs are aimed at turning a potential guest into a newcomer, and then into a regular customer, and in such a way that they feel the most desirable.

The restaurant business is an instant lottery. And every day is an opportunity for a completely new win. The purpose of such lotteries is to take

a reference point and attract people who have no idea about our institution, with the further transformation of them into our card file of regular customers. It can be carried out by distributing flyers, flyers, and other information leaflets about ongoing promotions.(2-P.24)

The most popular promotions are the following:

-held during large-scale holidays according to the principle: if you visit our restaurant on February 14, you will receive a 15% discount on visiting our restaurant during March;

-they allow you to get a bonus in the form of, for example, an individual souvenir or a permanent big discount during a certain time, number of visits, drawing special symbols or making a certain number of purchases

New formats. At the present stage, the development of IT technologies makes it possible to replace maps with virtual similar systems. These are various applications for iPad and Android-based tablet computers. There are more than 25 similar programs abroad. It is quite obvious that their appearance in Russia at the moment will not acquire serious proportions, but in the future, projects of this format are expected to appear in the next year, maybe two. You should make a reservation about the durability of such projects, which indicates that not everyone will be able to stay on the market and stay in use for a long time. Also, autonomous programs that can be managed via a tablet computer or a device located at the cash register of the institution have become very widespread in many countries. Such systems are easy to operate and maintain, but they still allow you to create a detailed database of customers. The latest fashion innovation is loyalty programs that can be combined with social networks. Site users participating in the project are rewarded not only for making purchases through points, but also for spreading information about the promotions they have used to their friends.

"Secret" techniques. The situation is such that not every enterprise can afford to create a particular program directly for its enterprise. This, as practice shows, is the privilege of the "powerful of this world", namely, enterprises of a network format. However, for establishments that work separately, there are a great many very effective activities that can create a delightful atmosphere, and leave an indelible impression on the guest's memory from visiting the restaurant.

Forgetfulness is not a vice. Having a savings card is great, but a person is so organized that rarely anyone carries all their cards with them (due to their variety and inability to predict their desires in a certain period of time, as well as the lack of a wallet that can hold all the necessary cards). If you are faced with a situation where the card is not available for any reason, do not deny the guest a discount by name, passport or other document. Don't deprive him of his friends, either opportunities to have a discount privilege at your establishment. This not only allows you to retain your guests and increase the number of their visits, but also creates the basis for attracting new visitors.

The very best should be rewarded. Do not build ornate systems for providing bonuses to customers, but try to involve regular customers in a certain competition. Select a certain number of your most frequent guests and encourage them with souvenirs or a compliment from the chef on their next visit.

The course is amazing. By properly organizing the programs, it is possible to summarize and store information about customers who have paid with a credit card. Moreover, after reaching a certain minimum order amount or the minimum number of purchases made, you can also encourage the guest, while not forgetting to express your gratitude for the invariability of the choice of your institution.

Timely congratulations. It is very appropriate to apply the statement of Nathan Mayer Rothschild in this situation "Who owns information owns the world." So, the daily collection of information about your customers will allow you to notify regular guests in advance about additional privileges in honor of their birthday. This can be an additional discount coupon combined with the main card, or a discount when booking a table for 8 people or more.

Individual orders offers for Loyal guests. Modern software allows you to track the list of ordered menu items or wine lists that the client prefers. Based on their preferences, give them a surprise that makes them feel like a welcome guest, whose individual characteristics are known to you.

Keep the brand. The "face" of your institution is a complex concept. Everyone-staff partner companies, brands, suppliers-should be on par with you. If you are positioning yourself as an elite restaurant, make an agreement with a company that is a supplier of alcoholic beverages about the possibility of providing several unique drinks as a gift to customers who enjoy the privileges of regular customers.

Hospitality is the most important thing that keeps a loyal guest's attitude. Perfect service will definitely smooth out the nuances that may arise as a result of not very good cooking by the restaurant's chef, and, conversely, an exquisitely prepared dish will definitely eliminate the inattention of the staff. But hospitality with a capital letter is, of course, when all services to the guest are provided at the highest level, without any nuances.(2-P.305)

5.Findings

The service staff simply needs to convey why each guest it is so important to us and is unique and unique in its kind. We can give you a few examples that will help you maintain the loyal attitude of our guests without causing financial damage to the company itself.

– Requirements for receiving phone calls. The main thing that needs to be conveyed to the staff, in particular to hostesses, is a certain list of 5-10 phrases. "Good afternoon. How can I help you!?" "Yes, of course, we will be glad to see you in our restaurant", "All the best, we are always glad to see you" and teach the staff to speak these phrases politely.

–Good automated systems will help you identify the caller at the time of receiving a call and specifying the customer's last name and initials by

the manager, as well as end the conversation with a polite phrase, for example: "Thank you, Toshmat Kenjaev. We will be glad to see you again."

-Trainings or competitions within the team to remember the names of guests are very popular. Staff should explain the importance of remembering the guest's name and the items they order most frequently in the menu. As a result, the next time you visit, the waiter may ask: "Excuse me , Ms Mukhabbat, do you want a cappuccino, as usual?". Thereby win the loyal attitude of the guest. It is necessary to teach waiters to pronounce "attentive phrases".

For example:

- It's convenient for you, maybe make the light a little brighter?
- If you're not feeling hot, why don't you turn on the air conditioner?
- Hello, great evening, don't you think? All this will create the impression of an individual attitude to the guest, and, of course, it will remain in his memory for a long time. It is necessary to take into account the presence of small, pleasant little things that can amaze guests. The company's budget will not suffer much from this. For example:

- calculator provided to the guest to calculate dinner costs;
- threads issued to the cloakroom attendant in order to sew a loop on the upper part guest's clothing;
- place a cleaning roller for clothes in the restroom
- put a shoe spray on the shelf.

Conclusion

The restaurant business is designed in such a way that there are no small things in it: it consists of the status and success of the enterprise is born. Each business owner chooses his own way of developing attracting new and retaining regular customers. This path is a purely individual decision of the manager, but this does not at all confirm the need to limit yourself to any one decision. All your actions, whether it is a compliment from the chef, a branded souvenir, a gift drink or a favorite song, should unobtrusively transfer your guests to the category of permanent ones who are absolutely confident in the personalized attitude towards them.

REFERENCES:

1. Arthur Middleton Hughes " The Customer Loyalty Solution: What Works (and What Doesn't) in Customer Loyalty Programs " 2003 (pp 24-338)
2. <https://www.touchbistro.com/blog/restaurant-loyalty-program-ideas/>

